

CAN BRAIDED COMPOSITES BE USED FOR CRUSHING ELEMENTS IN CARS ?

Hiroyuki Hamada

*Faculty of Textile Science, Kyoto Institute of Technology
Matsugasaki, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606, Japan*

SUMMARY: In this paper, braided composite I-beams are considered as possible candidates for crushing elements in cars. A description is given on the braiding process and the various mechanisms which can be used to produce different types of braided preforms, including I-beams. The mechanical performance of these braided I-beams under four-point bending is presented. The I-beams are also loaded in compression to investigate their progressive crush performance. The introduction of a chamfer on one end of the beams enabled high energy absorption values to be achieved through progressive crush. Investigation into the crush zone of partially crushed I-beams was also carried out to determine the energy absorption mechanisms which exist in such structures. A database of crush performance values (specific energy absorption) of composite tubes for a range of material systems is also presented, which has the potential to be used in the design of composite beams for crush elements in cars. From the crush and bending tests, it is concluded that the use of a braided composite in a car body is highly possible. To do so, several issues need to be addressed which are identified and discussed in this paper.

KEYWORDS: energy absorption mechanism, braids, I-beam, progressive crushing, bending properties, side member, glass fibre, impact test

INTRODUCTION

Recently, the increase in vehicle numbers has led to a rise in traffic accidents compared to the development of transportation. Consequently, there is a great demand on passive vehicle safety. In experiencing large impact, a rigid passenger compartment is needed to prevent harm to the occupants, which results in an increase in the vehicle weight. However, this leads to high impact energies and decelerations in vehicle collisions which has the potential to cause irreversible brain damage to the occupants. Therefore, the structural requirements of the passenger compartment should include high strength and light weight. Application of fibre reinforced plastics (FRP) to vehicle compartments can satisfy these requirements.

In the automotive industry, FRP have been used in applications such as bumpers, side panels and bonnet components, and has also become prominent in secondary structural components. However, despite the improved performance capabilities of FRP, the inherent high-costs associated with FRP restricts their use to high-performance niche applications.

It has been reported [1-6] that FRP tubes under axial compression load display high energy absorption performance, so that it is possible to protect occupants in a front collision by arranging the composite tube in front of a vehicle body, such as behind the bumper. To initiate crushing, a chamfer trigger is incorporated on one end of the tube. Failure starts at the

chamfered end, and the crushing zone propagates down the tube without catastrophic failure. This fracture behaviour is called progressive crushing.

The crashworthy performance of materials is commonly expressed with the specific energy absorption value, E_s , which is expressed by the following equation:

$$E_s = \frac{\bar{P}}{A\rho} \quad (1)$$

where, \bar{P} , A and ρ are the mean crush load, cross-sectional area and density, respectively. A unit is expressed by kJ/kg. For example, E_s of steel tube is 30 kJ/kg, whereas E_s of a glass cloth/epoxy composite tube is 70 kJ/kg. Progressive crushing behaviour contributes to the high E_s values of FRP.

In this paper, it is discussed whether or not it is possible for braided composites to be used in a car body as crush elements. Firstly, the braiding mechanism used to produce new braided fabrics is introduced. The most important point in the mechanics of braided composites is continuity of the reinforcing fibres. Although various braided fabrics were discussed in this paper, the concept of continuity was maintained in all the braids. Also, the mass production technique, referred to as Braiding Pultrusion Processing (BPP), which is expected to lead to a wider usage of braiding, is highlighted.

Secondly, the bending properties of braided I-beams are investigated. Among various kinds of braided fabrics, an I-beam was selected for crush elements of a car. The reason for this is that in Japan, about 23% of crush accidents resulting in fatalities are attributed to side impact [7]. It is necessary to consider not only front collision but also lateral collision in the design of a vehicle. The introduction of side impact bars has the potential to prevent fatalities resulting from side impact. Side members with I-shaped cross-sections can possess high bending strength due to the large second moment of area. If braided I-beams can be produced with high bending and crush properties, they would be ideally suited as side impact members.

Thirdly, the progressive crush behaviour of various composite tubes are presented in detail. This includes values of E_s for many kinds of material systems. It is emphasised that precise observation of fracture aspects is important in order to clarify the crushing mechanism. Finally, the crushing performance of a braided composite I-beam is described. The braided I-beam was found to possess high crush performance with an E_s value of 70 kJ/kg. The fracture mechanism is examined through observation of the crushed I-beam cross-section. The crush behaviour of the braided I-beam was found to be similar to that of a 0/90° tube. It is concluded that the use of a braided composite in a car body is highly possible.

BRAIDED I-BEAM

Braided Fabric

There are two kinds of basic braids; flat braid and tubular braid as shown in Fig. 1. The flat braid can be used to produce flat plates, whereas cylindrical shapes can be made from tubular braids. Fig. 2 shows schematically the fibre orientation state of the flat braid. The normal braided flat bar (see Fig. 2a) and that with the side edges cut off (see Fig. 2b) are referred to as "Non-cut" and "Cut" respectively. To compare the mechanical properties between Non-cut and Cut composites, tensile tests were carried out [8]. Tensile stress-strain curves of the composites are shown in Fig. 3. With the Non-cut specimens, the tensile stress increased linearly until it reached the maximum stress, while with the Cut specimens, the gradient of the

curve gradually decreased until the stress reached the maximum value. The maximum stress of the Non-cut specimens was much higher than that of Cut specimens. It can be said that the continuity of the fibres at the side edge strongly affects the tensile properties. Thus, in regards to continuous fibres, braided composites have superior characteristics compared to other fibre reinforced composites.

(a) (b)
 Fig. 1: Photographs of (a) flat braids and (b) tubular braids

(a) (b)
 Fig. 2: Schematic diagrams of (a) Non-cut and (b) Cut specimens

Fig. 3: Typical tensile stress-strain curves of Non-cut and Cut specimens

The importance of continuous fibres is highlighted in the mechanical joint problem. Fig. 4 shows schematically the fibre orientation around a hole. In the BH specimen, the fibre is

continuously oriented around the hole, whereas the fibres are discontinuous in the drilled hole of the MH specimen. Both specimens are used in mechanical joint test as shown in Fig. 5a. Fig. 5b indicates the load-displacement curve resulting from these joint tests. Clearly, the BH specimen has higher joint strength. Here, continuously oriented fibres are important for mechanical properties of composites, which can be easily realised by the braiding technique.

Braiding Mechanism

The conventional braiding mechanism consists of a taking up mechanism and spindle movement as shown in Fig. 6. Spindles move along the circle, which can be regarded as one-dimensional movement (1D). The formed fabric is taken up in the vertical direction, which is also regarded as one-dimensional movement (1D). Braided fabric with two-dimensional shapes such as flat and tubular braids can be fabricated with a combination of these two one-dimensional movements (1D + 1D = 2D).

Fig. 4: Schematics of (a) braided hole (BH) and (b) machined hole (MH) specimens

Fig. 5: Mechanical joint test: (a) Schematic of test set-up; and (b) Typical load-displacement response

Fig. 6: The conventional braiding mechanism

Table 1: List of braiding mechanism from low to high dimension

Taking up mechanism		Spindle movement
1-DS	+	1-DS
1-DR	+	1-DS
1-DS	+	1-DM
1-DS	+	2-D
3-D	+	1-DS

In order to fabricate near-net shape fabrics, new braiding mechanisms have to be considered. The concept of two sets of movement; taking up mechanism and spindle movement are very useful for creating new mechanisms. Table 1 lists our braiding mechanisms from low dimension to high dimension. The conventional braiding mechanism is indicated by 1-DS + 1-DS in this table. S refers to one way movement in the taking up mechanism and single truck in spindle movement. According to this table, new braiding mechanisms and fabricated braids are introduced in following sections.

1-DR + 1-DS

When reverse movement is applied to the taking up mechanism, which is referred to as 1-DR, the braided fabric returns in the opposite direction as shown in Fig. 7. If this reverse movement is repeated several times at certain intervals, and also the reversible points are changed during this process, a cylindrical braided through-the-thickness fabric can be produced as shown in Fig. 8. Interlaminar delamination would be suppressed by such through-the-thickness fabric due to interlamina reinforcement [9-14].

Fig. 7: The mandrel movement is reversed

Fig. 8: Cylindrical braided fabric with through-the-thickness fabric

Static lateral compression tests are performed on new braided composite cylinders. Fig. 9 shows the relation between the lateral compressive load and displacement. The braided cylinders are also compared with conventionally laminated tubes. Specimens with only three layers were considered in this test program. As can be seen from Fig. 9, the new braided composite cylinders, referred to as multi-reciprocal tube, maintains a high load since interlamina fracture is suppressed at the reversible point where the through-the-thickness fabrics exist. Whereas a sudden load drop is observed in laminated tubes due to interlamina

fracture which is not retarded. This difference is confirmed by observation of the fractured specimens.

Fig. 9: Relation between lateral compression load and displacement

1-DS + 1-DM

In this process, although the taking up mechanism is still one way in one dimension, spindle movements are not single because there are several tracks. Fig. 10 shows one example of this braiding mechanism, where 3 tracks are connected at some points. The spindles can move from one track into another as shown in Fig. 10. In this case, the spindle which begins in the outer track travels into the middle track and finally the inner track. Based on this mechanism a very unique braided cylinder can be fabricated. For example, the fibre can pass from the outer layer to the middle layer, and from the middle layer to the inner layer providing interlamina reinforcement equivalent to that of the multi-reciprocal cylinder.

Fig. 10: Tubular braid with through-the-thickness fibres

Another example is shown in Fig. 11 and 12. A cylindrical braided fabric with core materials can be fabricated. Four core materials are inserted between inner and middle layers, and between middle and outer layers. In this braiding process, the thickness of braided fabric depends on the thickness of the inner, middle and outer layers and thickness of the core materials. A light weight and thick composite can be manufactured by adopting foam material as core material. Fig. 12 shows a cross section of the cylindrical braided composite without core material which exhibits cells which are isolated from one another. This pipe is expected to be used as multi-functional pipe which can send different fluid at once.

Fig. 11: Schematic of a cylindrical braided fabric with core materials

Fig. 12: Photograph of a cross-section of a cylindrical braided composite without core materials

1-DS + 2-D

This braiding mechanism is the most important in this paper, because braided I-beams can be fabricated by this process. In this process, the taking up mechanism is one dimensional and one way. The track configuration is modified two-dimensionally according to the shape of the final products as shown in Fig. 13. In this process the spindle movements become more complex than the previous braiding mechanisms. For example, inadequate initial spindle setting pattern can not fabricate braided fabrics because a collision of spindles would occur. Also, regularity of the braided fabrics is changed according to the spindle collision.

Fig. 13: Two-dimensionally modified track configuration

Computer simulation which can predict adequate initial spindle setting pattern and fibre orientation state of formed braided fabrics must be developed. Fig. 14 shows an example of results obtained from computational simulation [15]. Accordingly, complex fibre orientation state is visible. Therefore, CAE system is needed in the braiding process [16,17]. Fig. 15 shows the flow chart of the braiding CAE system (BCAE), which consists of the simulation program for the design of the braiding machine and the numerical analysis method for the design of the final component. The CAE system consists of three steps; braided fabric, braided composite and braiding machine. The track configuration of a braiding machine for integrated braids can be designed using the simulation program. The initial spindle setting patterns that could provide a braiding structure with regular weaving pattern can also be provided. Using the numerical analysis method, the mechanical properties and fracture aspects of integrated braided composites can be predicted.

Fig. 16 shows the braiding machine and track configuration used to produce the I-beam. The track configuration was obtained by BCAE. It should be emphasised that the reinforcing fibres in the braided I-beam preform are continuously oriented. In order to reinforce the I-beam longitudinally, middle-end-fibres and axial fibres can be inserted. Fig. 17 illustrates the braided fibres which are continuously oriented and surround the axial fibres. This architecture is useful in the crushing mechanism described later in the paper.

Fig. 14: A result of computational simulation

Fig. 15: The flow chart of the braiding CAE system

Fig. 16: Braiding machine for I-beam and subsequent track configuration

Fig. 17: Schematic of a braided I-beam with axial fibres

3-D + 1-D

This braiding mechanism is a very interesting system, where by the taking up mechanism is 3-dimensional in spite of the one dimensional spindle movement, as shown in Fig. 18. The mandrel can move up and down and also rotate in any direction. Using this braiding mechanism multi-axial pipes can be fabricated (Fig. 18). Also, reinforcing fibres are continuously oriented in these products which enables a very high joint strength to be achieved [18]. Designers do not have to pay attention to the joint strength by using this pipe. In order to make the braiding machine for these pipes, great effort was needed technically with BCAE being used to assist in machine design. Fig. 19 shows the braiding machine used to produce braids with multiple braiding axes.

Fig. 18: Braiding mechanism for braid with multiple braiding axes

Fig. 19: Braiding machine for braid with multiple braiding axes

Braiding Pultrusion Process (BPP)

Resin impregnation for braided fabric is important mechanically and economically. Batch impregnation systems push up the cost of fabrication, so that continuous fabrication systems corresponding to mass production is needed.

Fig. 20 shows a schematic of the braiding pultrusion process [19]. Here, braided I-beams can be continuously fabricated. The impregnation device is placed between the braiding point and the braiding machine. Individual fibre strands under longitudinal tension meet the resin so that a higher degree of impregnation is achieved. Therefore at the entrance of the die, voids which may exist inside the braided fabric are squeezed out resulting in the completion of a high impregnation state. At the moment, the pultrusion conditions are as follows; pultrusion speed, pultrusion force and so on.

Fig. 20: Braiding pultrusion system

BENDING PROPERTIES OF BRAIDED I-BEAM

The braided fabric with I-shaped cross-section used in this paper consists of 63 glass fibre bundles (1150 tex, ER2310, Japan Electric Glass Co. Ltd.). The I-beam which consists of 100 unidirectional glass fibre bundles which were used as axial fibres in the flanges and web is referred to as G/G. While the I-beam with 76 carbon fibre bundles (800 tex, torayca, Tora Co.) used in the flanges and 24 glass fibre bundles in the web is referred to as G/CG. After impregnation with epoxy resin (EPIKOTE 828, Yuka Shell Epoxy Co. Ltd.) under vacuum, these I-beams were cured by the autoclave moulding method. The fibre volume contents were approximately 60%.

The dimensions of the bending specimen of the braided I-beam was approximately 18 mm in width and height. The thickness of both the flanges and web was 3 mm. Aluminium I-beams of the same dimensions were also prepared as a comparison. Four point bending tests with a 360 mm span and 120 mm mid span were conducted as shown in Fig. 21. Fig. 22 shows the relation between bending stress and deflection in three types of specimens. Bending properties obtained from experiment are summarised in Table 2. The bending strength of G/G and G/CG were 2.4, 2.8 times higher than that of aluminium, respectively. From these experimental results, it is understood that the braided I-beam has excellent bending properties.

Fig. 21: Schematic of the four point bend test

Fig. 22: Bending stress-deflection curves of three types of I-beam

Table 2: Bending modulus and strength under quasi-static condition

Specimen	Bending Modulus (GPa)	Bending Strength (MPa)
G/G	37.4	431
G/CG	73.5	520
Aluminium	71.8	183

PROGRESSIVE CRUSHING OF COMPOSITE TUBE

When an axial compressive load is applied to a composite tube, it leads to brittle fracture as shown in Fig. 23. The corresponding load-displacement curve is shown schematically in Fig. 24. On the other hand, when one end of the tube has a taper, this leads to progressive crushing because the tapered part acts as a trigger for fracture initiation. Fig. 25 shows the fracture mode and load-displacement curve of progressive crushing. The capability of energy

absorption for such a tube is very high because the enveloped area of the load-displacement curve is very large.

Fig. 23: Brittle fracture

Fig. 24: Load-displacement curve of brittle fracture

Fig. 25: Progressive crushing

Table 3 lists the specific energy absorption value (E_s) for various kinds of material systems [20-34]. E_s of carbon/PEEK exhibits the highest value and surprisingly in this data, a mean crushing load of 225 kN for a tube with an inner diameter of 50 mm and a wall thickness of 2.5 mm.

In the glass/epoxy composites, silane coupling agents are changed; one is amino silane and another is acryl silane. The former provides good adhesion but the latter does not. Fig. 26 shows the fracture aspects of crushed pipe in both material systems. The amino silane treated tube exhibits a splaying mode, whereas the acryl silane treated one shows a fragmentation mode. The properties of interface between fibre and matrix greatly affect the crushing behaviour. This result indicates the importance of interface.

Fig. 26: Fracture aspects of glass/epoxy tubes treated with (a) amino and (b) acryl silane coupling agents

In order to understand the fracture mechanism of crushed tubes, precise observations are needed. Fig. 27 shows the polished cross section of a carbon/PEEK tube which achieved the highest specific energy absorption value. Not only are inter- and/or intra-delaminations are observed but fibre fracture into small segments can also be clearly seen.

Fig. 27: Polished cross-section of carbon/PEEK

Table3-1 Energy absorption performances of metal tubes.

Material	(Quasi-static) Steel	(Impact)	(Quasi-static) Aluminum	(Impact)
Es (kJ/kg)	38.6	33.7	49.9	51.2

Table3-2 Energy absorption performances of glass cloth/epoxy tubes tested under different condition.

Test Condition	Quasi-static		Impact	
Surface Treatment	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl
Es (kJ/kg)	66.6	53.0	69.5	61.4

Table3-3 Energy absorption performances of glass cloth/epoxy tubes tested at different temperatures.

Temperature (°C)	-140		-80		-40		20	
Surface Treatment	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl
Es (kJ/kg)	104.3	90.1	96.6	68.4	79.0	57.2	66.6	53.0
Temperature (°C)	80		100		120		150	
Surface Treatment	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl
Es (kJ/kg)	50.1	43.0	33.8	32.8	—	—	—	—

Table3-4 Energy absorption performances of glass cloth/epoxy tubes hydrothermally aged in 80°C water for different time.

Immersion Time (hrs)	0		30		100	
Surface Treatment	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl
Es (kJ/kg)	66.6	53.0	58.5	43.3	58.6	46.3
Immersion Time (hrs)	300		1000		3000	
Surface Treatment	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl
Es (kJ/kg)	51.5	32.5	48.5	30.8	44.5	29.2

Table3-5 Energy absorption performances of glass cloth/epoxy tubes exposed in weather meter for different time.

Exposure Time (hrs)	0		500		1000	
Surface Treatment	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl
Es (kJ/kg)	66.6	53.0	71.9	56.7	69.9	55.8
Exposure Time (hrs)	1500		2000			
Surface Treatment	Amino	Acryl	Amino	Acryl		
Es (kJ/kg)	71.7	56.7	73.4	55.8		

Table3-6 Effect of t/D ratio on energy absorption performances of glass cloth/epoxy tubes.

Number of Ply	2	4	6	8	16	24	32	40
t/D ratio	0.008	0.015	0.022	0.029	0.062	0.097	0.130	0.179
Es (kJ/kg)	—	—	172	172	206	207	155	141
Number of Ply	8	16	42	80				
t/D ratio	0.011	0.022	0.059	0.110				
Es (kJ/kg)	—	196	157	148				

Table3-7 Effect of taper angle on energy absorption performances of glass cloth/epoxy tubes.

Taper Angle (°)	15	45	75
Es (kJ/kg)	67.9	66.0	67.1

Table3-8 Energy absorption performances of glass cloth/epoxy tubes in off-axis test.

Inclination Angle (°)	0	5	10	15	20	
Es (kJ/kg)	Quasi-static	68.8	67.2	65.3	58.1	43.1
	Impact	68.1	68.0	65.5	62.8	60.9

Table3-9 Energy absorption performances of glass cloth/epoxy tubes by using of the jig.

Jig	Flat Platen	For External Splaying Mode	For Internal Splaying Mode
Es (kJ/kg)	67.1	77.9	116.2
Impact	66.7	85.3	86.8

Table3-10 Energy absorption performances of glass cloth/epoxy tubes in different impact speed.

Impact Speed (km/h)	20.0	30.0	50.0
Es (kJ/kg)	68.6	71.8	69.4

Table3-11 Energy absorption performances of FW-FRP tubes with different fiber reinforcement under static condition.

Material	GF/Epoxy			CF/Epoxy			KF/Epoxy		
Fiber Orientation Angle (°)	±15	±45	±75	±15	±45	±75	±15	±45	±75
Es (kJ/kg)	39.8	25.3	40.7	70.3	22.6	53.3	25.6	33.5	41.6

Table3-12 Energy absorption performances of FW-FRP tubes with different fiber reinforcement under impact condition.

Material	GF/Epoxy			CF/Epoxy			KF/Epoxy		
Fiber Orientation Angle (°)	±15	±45	±75	±15	±45	±75	±15	±45	±75
Es (kJ/kg)	17.2	40.5	51.2	67.3	62.5	55.3	36.4	39.1	55.3

Table3-13 Energy absorption performances of CF/DF Hybrid FW tubes with different fiber architecture.

Fiber Architecture	DF100%		Interlamina CF/DF/CF		Intralamina CF/DF=1/1	Intralamina CF/DF=3/1
	±10	±30	±10	±30	±10	±10
Fiber Orientation Angle (°)						
Es (kJ/kg)	29.0	—	67.1	31.0	48.0	76.4

cf. Dyneema is a ultra-high molecular weight Polyethylene fiber has high strength and modulus.

Table3-14 Energy absorption performances of CF/DF Hybrid Cloth tubes with different fiber architecture.

Fiber Architecture	DF100% Plain Cloth		Warp:CF, Weft:DF Plain Cloth		Warp,Weft:CF,DF Plain Cloth	
	0,90	±45	CF:0 DF:90	CF:90 DF:0	0,90	±45
Fiber Orientation Angle (°)						
Es (kJ/kg)	32.1	—	49.5	35.5	47.3	49.0

Table3-15 Energy absorption performances of CF/PEEK tubes with different fiber orientation angle.

Fiber Orientation Angle (°)	0	±5	±10	±15	±20	±25	±30
Es (kJ/kg)	194	205	225	214	202	181	—

Table3-16 Energy absorption performances of Glass/PEEK tubes with different fiber orientation angle.

Fiber Orientation Angle (°)	0	±5	±10	±15	±20	±25	±30
Es (kJ/kg)	143	113	191	172	171	—	—

Table3-17 Effect of cooling rate on energy absorption performances of Carbon/PEEK 15° tubes.

Cooling Rate (°C/min)	Rapid Cooling -95.5	Gradual Cooling -8.2	Slow Cooling -0.7
Es (kJ/kg)	219	197	197

Table3-18 Energy absorption performances of CF/PEEK tubes under Impact condition.

Fiber Orientation Angle (°)	0	±5	±10
Es (kJ/kg)	91.2	99.3	98.0

Table3-19 Energy absorption performances of CFRTP tubes with different matrix resin.

Material (0°)	CF/PEEK	CF/PEI	CF/PI	CF/PAS
Es (kJ/kg)	225	155	131	128

According to these observations we propose an equation which describe the contribution of each fracture factors to total energy absorption value as follows:

$$U = U_{sp} + U_{lc} + U_{de} + U_{ff} + U_{fr} + U_{\sigma} + \text{others}$$

The detail of this equation is shown in Fig. 28. It is considered that the total energy absorption performance U in progressive crushing mainly consists of six energy absorption mechanisms. They are energy absorbed by the splitting of fronds, required for central crack, absorbed by delamination of fronds, required for fibre fracture, associated with frictional heating and that generated by bending deformation.

Fig. 28: Contribution of each fracture factor

It is clear that fracture aspects are very important for designing crushing elements. Therefore, a database was established for the crushing performances of composites, which can be easily used in the design of a car body. Fig. 29 shows a diagram of a system for both software and hardware. Software used in this study was for a normal database that can treat image data, because the fracture aspects should be included. The image data was input through an image scanner for published data and video signal port for a new result. In order to use large data memory an MO device was used for storing data. Main memory for using this database was only 0.6 MB.

Fig. 29: Diagram of system for software and hardware

The database includes load-displacement curves, E_s values and other numerical data, out view of fractured materials, microscopic observations are included as well as material and experimental conditions.

CRUSHING BEHAVIOUR OF BRAIDED I-BEAM

Specimens and Experimental Method

Compressive tests under quasi-static and impact conditions were carried out in thickness, width and axial directions of braided I-beams (G/G type). The length of the specimens used in this study was 30 mm. To initiate progressive crushing a chamfer or notch was machined onto one end of the specimen as shown in Fig. 30. The chamfer acts as a trigger for progressive crush. The specimens compressed in the thickness direction were referred to as Type A and B. The Type B specimen had a notch machined on one end. The specimens compressed in width and axial directions respectively were referred to as Types C and D and Types E and F. Specimen Types D and F where machined with a chamfer at one end.

Fig. 30: Types of braided I-beams tested under compression

Quasi-static tests were performed using an Instron Universal Testing Machine (Type 4206) at a constant cross-head speed of 2 mm/min. Impact tests were performed using a drop-test facility (The Japan Automobile Research Institute). The drop plate weight of 49.0 kg was dropped from a height of 0.88 m to give an impact velocity of 15 km/h, where a stopper was set to keep a constant crushing displacement. The signals from the load cells located beneath the platform were fed to the analog-digital converter. The digitised signal was then filtered with a cut-off frequency of 1 kHz. The data representing the load-time history of the impact tests were processed to produce load-displacement curves.

The crushed specimens were cast in polyester resin to observe the crush zone morphology. The cross-sections in the web region were polished and photographed on an optical microscope.

Results

The load-displacement curves in quasi-static and impact tests are shown in Fig. 31. Types D and F specimens which had a trigger at one end displayed small load fluctuation, while Type C and E specimens which had no trigger displayed a high peak load in the early stages.

Energy absorption performances obtained from load-displacement curves are summarised in Table 4. Type F exhibited the highest E_s , about 70 kJ/kg in both quasi-static and impact tests. It was clear that braided I-beam had excellent energy absorption performances in the axial direction, similar to that found with commercial glass cloth/epoxy tubes previously studied.

Fig. 31: Load-displacement curves of braided I-beam under (a) quasi-static and (b) impact conditions

Table 4: Energy absorption performances of braided I-beams

Test Condition	Type	Mean Crush Load (kN)	Maximum Crush Load (kN)	Specific Absorption (kJ/kg)
Static	A	-	13.3	-
	B	6.3	10.0	13.7
	C	9.1	17.5	21.2
	D	9.2	10.8	21.4
	E	13.3	27.5	50.5
	F	19.0	20.9	70.0
Impact	B	5.3	13.3	11.5
	C	-	27.0	-
	D	10.5	12.9	24.5
	E	11.7	55.0	44.5
	F	19.6	26.1	74.5

Photographs of crush zones of braided I-beams after quasi-static and impact tests are shown in Fig. 32. In quasi-static tests, Types B, D and F with a trigger showed progressive crushing. Types C and E which had no trigger crushed axially from one end of the specimen, however showed a fatal crack at the web section. On the other hand, in the impact test, Types C and E crushed in a brittle manner while Types B, D, F displayed progressive crushing, same as that observed in quasi-static tests. Accordingly, for specimens with no chamfer catastrophic fractures were observed, so that the load abruptly decreased and was highly serrated. In contrast, specimens with triggers showed progressive crushing which resulted in a constant load.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 32: Photographs of crush aspects of braided I-beams under (a) quasi-static and (b) impact conditions.

Detailed photomicrographs of cross-sections cut through the crush zone parallel to the axis of the web in quasi-static tested Type F specimens are shown in Fig. 33 and their schematic diagrams are shown in Fig. 34. To clarify the crushing mechanism, the development of the crush zone in the braided I-beam was examined by observation of crush zones in four stages of partially crushed I-beams. Stage 1 represents the crush zone morphology during the increase of the load. Stage 2 corresponds to the crush zone in reaching the peak load. Stage 3 shows the crush zone at the initial stage of the stable crush load region and Stage 4 shows the crush zone during stable crushing. In Stage 1 kinking and delaminations between plies of unidirectional fibres were observed in the chamfer region. In Stage 2 the debris wedge consisting of fractured fibres and resin was seen, and a longitudinal crack had also formed beneath the debris wedge. In Stage 3 the wedge increases in size, and then in Stage 4, the central crack observed in the previous stage disappears, instead delamination at the fronds and fibre fracture are clearly observed.

Fig. 33: Photomicrographs of web cross-sections of quasi-static tested Type F I-beams at various load stages

Discussion

For unidirectional glass fibre/epoxy composite materials, compressive strength is lower than tensile strength because of buckling and splitting in general. This is mainly due to the low fracture toughness of epoxy resin. For conditions to exhibit high crush load under axial

compression, two points are considered as follows. One is that the composites must contain many unidirectional fibres in the compressive direction. The other is that little fracture such as shear crack, splitting and so on occurred. For instance, unidirectional carbon fibre/PEEK tubes displayed the highest E_s values (200 kJ/kg) that has been recorded in the literature. This reason for this is that splitting of unidirectional carbon fibres was not seen due to high fracture toughness of PEEK resin [35].

To increase the compressive strength for glass fibre reinforced composite tubes, Hull [36] had investigated the effect of different ratios of hoop and axial fibres of composite tube on crushing performance. Several kinds of tubes fabricated from glass cloth polyester prepreg materials were prepared with different warp and weft ratios. According to his findings, the crushing performance had an optimum range between a hoop:axial ratio of 1:1 and 1:4. This is mainly due to a number of fractures occurring at the fronds such as interlaminar and fibre fracture. The hoop constraints further greatly contribute to the formation of these fractures.

Fig. 34: Schematic of the web cross-sections of quasi-static tested Type F I-beams at various load stages

In the case of braided I-beams, the ratio of braiding fibre and axial fibre is 1 to 1.5. If the braiding fibre can be regarded as the hoop fibre, it is considered this ratio is appropriate for obtaining high stable crush load according to Hull's suggestion. The resin used in the braided I-beams have a low fracture toughness, however, still displayed high values of E_s , same as those of glass cloth/epoxy tubes. This is because the axial fibres which are placed into the braided fabric are supported by the continuous structure of the braiding fibres.

CAN BRAIDED COMPOSITES BE USED FOR CRUSHING ELEMENTS IN CARS ?

In the previous sections, details were given on two major topics; braided composites and the crushing behaviour of composites. Consequently, the braided I-beams proposed in this paper have the potential to be used as crush elements in a car body. However, there are several requirements which need to be addressed before braided I-beams can be used. Here, we would like to list these requirements and ask researchers who are interested in composite materials to address these requirements.

Integrated Composite Structure System

A braided I-beam itself possesses high bending and high crushing performance, however, a connecting method or integrated method to a car body has to be considered. A braided hole has a high mechanically fastened joint strength, as shown earlier in the paper, so it is expected that an integrated structure would also have a similar high performance.

Durability of Composite Structures

A braided I-beam may possibly be exposed to severe environments, particularly when it is designed for an outer panel of the car body. We performed some experiments for crushing behaviour of composite cylinders exposed in weather meters for long periods of time as shown in Table 3-5. The results did not show any change to the crush performance, however, environmental tests on braided I-beams has never been carried out.

Dependence of Crushing Speed

In this paper we described the results of a 15 km/h speed test. For actual usage, the dependence of crushing speed on E_s has to be measured.

Conversely, a collision or an accident at slow speed will cause a small amount of damage inside the braided I-beam. This may result in a decrease in the crushing performance for a severe accident. It is necessary to know what damage is generated in a low speed accident and preferably what damage mechanisms are introduced to estimate crushing performance of braided I-beams.

Database

The database described earlier in the paper is established for designers of car bodies to understand the crushing performance of FRP composite materials in detail. The database will be distributed in MO disk style.

However, the most important factor is that the database provides reassurance on crushing behaviour of FRP. Usually, the crushing behaviour can not be believed by the persons who have not observed actual testing. Also people misunderstand that properties of composite materials have large scatter, so that they do not believe or are not able to understand crushing.

Developing a large data base would assist in enabling everyone to understand the crushing performance. Here, four factors have been identified which need to be conquered for the actual usage of braided I-beams in car bodies. There are many other factors to be considered,

so we need to change the discussion or argument, particularly from the car industry, or undertake co-research work for appropriate usage of composite materials.

CONCLUSIONS

Braided composite I-beams were considered as possible candidates for crushing elements in cars. They were shown to possess excellent bending properties compared to conventional aluminium, important in the application of side members. The introduction of a trigger mechanism allowed composite I-beams to display excellent progressive crush characteristics, similar to those exhibited by composite tubes. Specific energy absorption values reached 70 kJ/kg for braided I-beams. The structure of the braided I-beam was found to be suitable for progressive crushing because axial fibres are tied up by braided fibre.

Therefore, it can be concluded that braided I-beams are useful for impact energy absorbers in lateral and frontal collisions. They can be introduced into the car body as side members designed to absorb both front and side impact. However, for braided I-beams to fulfil this potential, several issues need to be addressed. These include: integration of the composite structure; durability of the composite materials; dependencies on crushing speed; and the creation of a database of progressive crush characteristics.

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